

1 **Fetal exposure to phthalates and body mass index from infancy to adolescence. The**
2 **Generation R Study.**

3
4 **Short title: Maternal phthalates and childhood body mass index**

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22
23 **Word count manuscript: 4578**

24 **Word count abstract: 250**

25 **Key words:** prenatal exposure, phthalates, body mass index, childhood

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32

33 **ABSTRACT**

34 Prenatal exposure to phthalates might influence the development of childhood obesity. Most previous
35 studies used body mass index (BMI) at a specific age instead of BMI development, which might be a
36 better indicator of later health. We aimed to assess the association of prenatal phthalate exposure with
37 longitudinal BMI development from infancy to adolescence. Among 1,379 mother-child pairs from a
38 population-based cohort study, phthalate concentrations were measured in maternal spot urine
39 samples, collected during first, second and third trimester. We estimated age- and sex-adjusted BMI
40 standard deviation scores (SDS) at 6 months and 1, 2, 3, 4, 6, 10 and 13 years. We examined the
41 associations of maternal phthalate urine concentrations during pregnancy with repeated measures of
42 BMI using linear mixed effects models. An interquartile range higher natural log-transformed
43 maternal first trimester high-molecular weight phthalate and di-2-ethylhexylphthalate (DEHP) urine
44 concentrations were associated with a -0.10 (95% confidence interval (CI) -0.15 to -0.04), and -0.09
45 (95% CI -0.15 to -0.04) lower age- and sex-adjusted BMI at 6 months. An interquartile range higher
46 natural log-transformed maternal first trimester phthalic acid and low-molecular weight phthalate
47 urine concentrations were associated with a 0.11 (95% CI 0.03 to 0.18) and 0.13 (95% CI 0.04 to 0.21)
48 higher age- and sex-adjusted BMI at 13 years old. No significant associations were observed for
49 maternal second and third trimester phthalate urine concentrations with BMI. Thus, higher maternal
50 phthalate metabolites urine concentrations appear to be related to lower BMI at early ages but with
51 higher BMI at later ages.

52

53

54 **1. INTRODUCTION**

55 Phthalates are non-persistent endocrine disrupting chemicals that are used as plasticizers and solvents
56 in many consumer items, such as cosmetics and food packaging materials (Koniecki et al., 2011;
57 Schechter et al., 2013). The effects of phthalates might start prenatally, as phthalates can cross the
58 placenta (Mose et al., 2007). The ‘Developmental Origins of Health and Disease (DOHaD)’ hypothesis
59 suggests that being exposed to certain environmental factors during vulnerable periods, such as the
60 fetal period, may have adverse and lifelong effects on development and health throughout life (Barker,
61 2007). In particular, it has been suggested that exposure to phthalates during fetal life might influence
62 growth and body mass index (BMI) by affecting the lipid and carbohydrate metabolism, inducing
63 oxidative stress or causing epigenetic changes (Campioli et al., 2014; Feige et al., 2007; Manikkam et
64 al., 2013; Taxvig et al., 2012).

65 Several previous studies have examined the association of maternal urine concentrations of
66 phthalate metabolites with childhood obesity (Agay-Shay et al., 2015; Berger et al., 2021; Botton et
67 al., 2016; Bowman et al., 2019; Buckley et al., 2016; Etzel et al., 2022; Ferguson et al., 2022; Gao et
68 al., 2022; Gao et al., 2023; Güil-Oumrait et al., 2022; Harley et al., 2017; Heggeseth et al., 2019;
69 Kupsco et al., 2022; Lee et al., 2020; Li et al., 2021; Maresca et al., 2016; Montes et al., 2022; Nidens
70 et al., 2021; Shoaff et al., 2017; Sol et al., 2020; Stevens et al., 2023; Svensson et al., 2021; Vafeiadi
71 et al., 2018; Valvi et al., 2015; Vrijheid et al., 2020; Yang et al., 2017; Yang et al., 2018). Most of
72 these studies assessed BMI at relatively young ages (below 10 years old) and in small populations, and
73 reported positive (Berger et al., 2021; Botton et al., 2016; Harley et al., 2017; Li et al., 2021), null
74 (Agay-Shay et al., 2015; Buckley et al., 2016; Etzel et al., 2022; Güil-Oumrait et al., 2022; Nidens et
75 al., 2021; Sol et al., 2020; Vafeiadi et al., 2018; Vrijheid et al., 2020), or negative associations
76 (Bowman et al., 2019; Shoaff et al., 2017; Stevens et al., 2023; Yang et al., 2017), with four studies
77 reporting sex-specific associations (Lee et al., 2020; Maresca et al., 2016; Montes et al., 2022; Valvi et
78 al., 2015). In addition to the health risks of having obesity at a certain stage in life, research has
79 evolved to understand that adverse BMI development is a stronger predictor of subsequent health than
80 BMI at a certain age (Barker et al., 2005). However, a smaller number of studies examined prenatal
81 phthalate exposure in relation to BMI or adiposity outcomes measured longitudinally throughout

82 childhood (Botton et al., 2016; Buckley et al., 2016; Ferguson et al., 2022; Gao et al., 2022; Gao et al.,
83 2023; Harley et al., 2017; Heggeseth et al., 2019; Kupsco et al., 2022; Montes et al., 2022; Svensson
84 et al., 2021; Valvi et al., 2015; Yang et al., 2018). Those studies showed inconsistent results with
85 somewhat more positive associations, most only included one or two measures of maternal phthalate
86 urine concentrations and had small sample sizes (Botton et al., 2016; Buckley et al., 2016; Ferguson et
87 al., 2022; Gao et al., 2022; Harley et al., 2017; Heggeseth et al., 2019; Kupsco et al., 2022; Montes et
88 al., 2022; Svensson et al., 2021; Valvi et al., 2015; Yang et al., 2018). Thus, assessing the effects of
89 fetal exposure to phthalates on BMI measured longitudinally at multiple time points from infancy until
90 adolescence, rather than one measurement taken at any individual age, is of utmost importance.

91 In this prospective population-based cohort study of 1,379 mother-child pairs, we examined
92 the associations of maternal urine phthalate metabolite concentrations during first, second and third
93 trimesters of pregnancy with repeated measures of BMI from infancy to adolescence.

94

95 **2. METHODS**

96 **2.1 Study design**

97 The present study is part of a larger research line into the effects of endocrine disruptors on childhood
98 health, embedded in the Generation R Study, which is a population-based prospective cohort study
99 that started during early fetal life and was performed in Rotterdam, the Netherlands (Kooijman et al.,
100 2016). The study was approved by the Medical Ethics Committee of Erasmus MC, University Medical
101 Center in Rotterdam. Written informed consent was obtained from all participants. Phthalate urine
102 concentrations were measured in 1,405 mothers, of singleton children, who had collected spot urine
103 samples during the first, second or third trimester of pregnancy and who participated in postnatal
104 studies. The socio-demographic and lifestyle characteristics of these women were comparable to the
105 whole Generation R cohort (Philips et al., 2018). In this study, we only included mothers for whom
106 phthalate urine concentrations were available in the three trimesters of pregnancy, leading to a final
107 sample size of 1,379 mothers and their singleton children (the specific sample per outcome is given in
108 **Supplemental Figure S1**).

109

110 **2.2 Maternal phthalate urine concentrations**

111 Methods of collection, transportation, and analysis of phthalate urine concentrations within the
112 Generation R Study have been described elsewhere (Philips et al., 2018). Between February 2004 and
113 July 2005, we collected spot urine samples from each woman during the first (median [25th-75th
114 percentiles] 12.9 [12.1-14.5] weeks of gestation), second (median [25th-75th percentiles] 20.4 [19.9-
115 20.9] weeks of gestation) and third (median [25th-75th percentiles] 30.2 [29.9-30.8] weeks of
116 gestation) trimester and measured phthalate metabolite concentrations. Phthalate metabolites were
117 grouped by parent phthalate molecule and their molecular weight (expressed in weighted molar sums).
118 We only used information on a specific phthalate metabolite if < 80% of the concentrations were
119 below the limit of detection (LOD). The concentrations below LOD were replaced by $LOD/\sqrt{2}$ and the
120 phthalate urine concentrations were converted to $\mu\text{mol/g}$ creatinine to account for urinary dilution
121 (Hornung RW, 1990). **Table 1** shows the descriptive statistics of the individual and grouped phthalates
122 per trimester and the percentage of values below the LOD. We also calculated the intraclass
123 correlation coefficients (ICC) between the natural log-transformed phthalates (in nmol/L) over
124 pregnancy, which ranged from 0.10 to 0.40 (**Table 1**). We calculated the pregnancy-averaged
125 phthalate urine concentrations for the individual and grouped phthalates that had > 20% of the
126 concentrations above the LOD in all three trimesters.

127

128 **2.3 Childhood body mass index**

129 Childhood length or height and weight were measured according to standardized procedures at the
130 ages of 6 months, 1, 2, 3, and 4 years in community health centres. At ages 6, 10 and 13 years old,
131 children visited our dedicated research facility, where height and weight were measured. We
132 calculated BMI (in kg/m^2) at each time point and then calculated age- and sex-adjusted standard
133 deviation scores (SDS) for all BMI measurements using Dutch reference growth charts (Fredriks et al.,
134 2000). The number of children in which BMI was measured differed per time point. The median
135 number of postnatal BMI measurements was 6 (25th-75th percentiles: 5-7; full range: 1-8).
136 Additionally, at each time point, age and sex-specific BMI z-scores were derived and categorized as

137 underweight or normal weight (≤ 1 SD) and overweight/obesity (> 1 SD), based on the WHO growth
138 standard and reference values (de Onis et al., 2007; WHO, 2006).

139

140 **2.4 Covariates**

141 Information on the following covariates was collected from questionnaires during pregnancy: maternal
142 age at enrollment, pre-pregnancy weight, educational level, ethnicity, folic acid supplement use,
143 parity, smoking habits and alcohol consumption. Maternal height was measured at enrollment and
144 used to calculate pre-pregnancy BMI (kg/m^2). Participating mothers filled in a validated semi-
145 quantitative food frequency questionnaire at enrollment that covered the average diet during the first
146 trimester of pregnancy and that information was used to estimate the maternal diet quality score
147 (Klipstein-Grobusch et al., 1998; Tielemans et al., 2016).

148

149 **2.5 Statistical analysis**

150 Characteristics of the study sample regarding the exposures, outcomes and covariates were
151 summarized. For all analyses, the maternal phthalate urine concentrations were adjusted for the
152 creatinine concentration and natural log-transformed. This conversion was performed to reduce
153 variability and to further account for right skewedness of the distribution. Subsequently, the exposures
154 were standardized by the interquartile range (IQR) to ease the interpretation of the effect sizes. We
155 created a correlation matrix between all first trimester natural log-transformed grouped and individual
156 phthalates (in nmol/L) and between all childhood age- and sex-adjusted BMI measurements using
157 Pearson correlation analysis. As part of the model-building process, we assessed nonlinearity using
158 generalized additive mixed models fitted with thin plate regression splines. These spline-based models
159 were compared to those incorporating only simple linear terms, using the Akaike Information
160 Criterion (AIC), residuals diagnostics and other diagnostic plots. We inspected the pattern of
161 associations of the phthalate concentrations with childhood BMI using generalized additive models
162 and non-linearity was not observed. Thus, no consistent evidence was found to support a nonlinear
163 relationship between BMI and age. Consequently, linear mixed effect models were used to assess the
164 associations of first, second or third trimester, or pregnancy-averaged phthalate concentrations with

165 childhood age- and sex-adjusted BMI SDS measured repeatedly during childhood. A random intercept
166 and slope were included in all models. Additionally, we included an interaction term between the
167 trimester-specific or pregnancy-averaged phthalate urine concentrations and child's age to allow the
168 exposure-outcome association to change during childhood. For associations that differed by timing of
169 outcome measurement, we used plots to illustrate the associations and the age at BMI measurement
170 was centered at 6 months, 6 years and 13 years to obtain the effect estimates at these specific time
171 points. As a sensitivity analysis, we also assessed these associations for the individual maternal urine
172 phthalate concentrations. We additionally performed linear regression analyses to assess the
173 associations of first, second or third trimester, or pregnancy-averaged phthalate concentrations with
174 childhood age- and sex-adjusted BMI SDS at all ages separately.

175 Potential confounders were defined as any lifestyle, sociodemographic or nutritional
176 characteristics that were related to both prenatal exposure to phthalates and childhood BMI in previous
177 studies (relationships were presented in a directed acyclic graph (DAG) in **Supplemental Figure S2**).
178 Potential confounders were included in the models if they fulfilled the graphical criteria for
179 confounding (i.e., if they block an open backdoor path) and changed the effect estimates >10% for at
180 least one of the outcomes (Santos et al., 2019). Since the effects of endocrine disrupting chemicals on
181 childhood growth may be sex-specific, we tested for statistical interaction of the maternal phthalate
182 urine concentrations with child's sex in these associations (Qian et al., 2020). We did not find
183 statistically significant interactions in the linear mixed effect models. However, as a sensitivity
184 analysis, we stratified the analysis based on sex. We performed two sensitivity analyses in the linear
185 regression models. First, to examine the independent associations of maternal first, second and third
186 trimester phthalate urine concentrations, we simultaneously included the exposures during all three
187 trimesters in one linear regression model, after ruling out potential problems with multicollinearity.
188 Second, to assess the effect of adjusting the exposure for creatinine, we performed the analysis with
189 exposures in nmol/L with creatinine added as a covariate into the model. Each p-value was compared
190 with a threshold which was defined as 0.05 divided by the effective number of independent tests,
191 which was estimated based on the correlation between the exposures to correct for multiple hypothesis
192 testing, leading to a p-value threshold of 0.007 (Li et al., 2012). To maintain statistical power and

193 reduce bias due to missing information on covariates, we performed multiple imputation according to
194 the Markov Chain Monte Carlo method. The percentage of missing values for covariates ranged from
195 0-25%. No missing outcome measurements were imputed. We created ten imputed datasets and
196 identified no substantial differences between the original and imputed datasets. All presented results
197 are based on these pooled imputed datasets. Statistical analyses were performed using the Statistical
198 Package of Social Sciences version 25.0 for Windows (SPSS Inc., Chicago, IL, USA) and R software
199 (version 4.1.2). The software package *mgcv* was used to perform the generalized additive mixed
200 models and generalized additive models and package *nlme* was used to perform the linear mixed
201 effects models.

202

203 **3. RESULTS**

204 **3.1 Subject characteristics**

205 **Table 2** and **Table 3** show the descriptive statistics for covariates and outcome measures, respectively.
206 The mean age of the mothers was 30.5 years, 61.9% was European, 50.3% was higher educated,
207 80.6% used folic acid supplementation during pregnancy and the median pre-pregnancy BMI was 22.7
208 kg/m² (**Table 2**). Depending on the age of measurement, the median BMI varied between 15.7 and
209 18.8 kg/m² and the percentage of children being overweight or obese varied between 10.1 and 15.7%
210 (**Table 3**). The Pearson correlations between the individual and grouped natural log-transformed
211 phthalates (in nmol/L) from first trimester (heat map in **Supplemental Figure S3**) and between the
212 age- and sex-adjusted childhood BMI measurements (heat map in **Supplemental Figure S4**) were
213 moderate to strong.

214

215 **3.2 Maternal phthalate urine concentrations and BMI from infancy to adolescence**

216 After adjusting for potential confounders, no associations were found for maternal second trimester
217 phthalic acid (PA) and second and third trimester HMWP, DEHP and DNOP (**Table 4**, basic models
218 are presented in **Supplemental Table S1**). The associations of maternal first and third trimester PA,
219 LMWP in all trimesters and first trimester HMWP, DEHP and DNOP with childhood BMI differed
220 based on timing of BMI measurement (p-values for interaction with age at time of measurement <

221 0.05, **Table 4**). These associations were plotted and showed a general trend towards lower age- and
222 sex-adjusted BMI SDS at younger ages and higher age- and sex-adjusted BMI SDS at older ages
223 (**Figure 1**). An IQR higher natural log-transformed maternal first trimester PA, HMWP, DEHP and
224 DNOP urine concentrations was associated with a -0.07 (95% confidence interval (95% CI) -0.12 to -
225 0.01), -0.10 (95% CI -0.15 to -0.04), -0.09 (95% CI -0.15 to -0.04) and -0.07 (-0.13 to -0.02) lower
226 age- and sex-adjusted BMI SDS at 6 months old, of which the associations of first trimester HMWP
227 and DEHP remained significant after correction for multiple testing. An IQR higher natural log-
228 transformed maternal first and third trimester PA and first trimester LMWP urine concentration was
229 associated with a 0.11 (95% CI 0.03 to 0.18), 0.11 (95% CI 0.03 to 0.19) and 0.13 (95% CI 0.04 to
230 0.21) higher age- and sex-adjusted BMI SDS at 13 years old, although the association of third
231 trimester PA did not remain significant after correction for multiple testing. The associations found for
232 maternal LMWP urine concentrations were driven mostly by monoethylphthalate (mEP) and
233 monomethylphthalate (mMP), while the associations for maternal HMWP urine concentrations were
234 driven mostly by the DEHP metabolites (**Supplemental Table S2** and **Supplemental Table S3**). The
235 associations for the pregnancy-averaged maternal urine phthalate concentrations were comparable to
236 the trimester-specific associations, although the effect estimates were somewhat weaker
237 (**Supplemental Table S4**). When exploring the associations among boys and girls separately, after
238 adjusting for potential confounders, these associations were comparable between boys and girls and
239 between the sex-specific analysis and the analysis in the whole cohort (**Supplemental Table S5** and
240 **Supplemental Table S6** for boys and **Supplemental Table S7** and **Supplemental Table S8** for girls).

241

242 **3.3 Maternal phthalate urine concentrations and BMI at each age across infancy and** 243 **adolescence**

244 After adjustment for potential confounders, higher concentrations of multiple phthalates were
245 associated with a lower age- and sex-adjusted BMI at 1, 2 or 3 years (**Supplemental Table S9**, basic
246 models are presented in **Supplemental Table S10**). The associations of first trimester HMWP and
247 DEHP with age- and sex-adjusted BMI at 1 and 2 years and second trimester DNOP with age- and
248 sex-adjusted BMI at 2 years remained significant after correction for multiple testing. Higher first and

249 third trimester maternal urine PA concentrations were associated with higher age- and sex-adjusted
250 BMI SDS at 13 years old, although these associations did not remain significant after correction for
251 multiple testing. The associations of the pregnancy-averaged maternal HMWP, DEHP and DNOP
252 urine concentrations were comparable to the trimester-specific associations. The mutually adjusted
253 model and the model with creatinine as a covariate in the model showed similar results, although the
254 associations were somewhat diminished for the model with creatinine as a covariate (**Supplemental**
255 **Table S11** and **Supplemental Table S12**). When assessing the associations of maternal urine
256 phthalate concentrations with the odds of developing overweight or obesity, we observed that, after
257 correction for multiple testing, higher maternal urine HMWP and DEHP concentration in first
258 trimester were associated with a lower odds of having overweight or obesity at 12 months
259 (**Supplemental Table S13**).

260

261 **4. DISCUSSION**

262 **4.1 Main findings**

263 We found an association of higher maternal urine HMWP and DEHP concentrations with lower age-
264 and sex-adjusted BMI SDS at younger ages within this population-based prospective cohort study. On
265 the other hand, higher maternal urine PA and LMWP concentrations were associated with higher age-
266 and sex-adjusted BMI SDS at older ages. It seems that first trimester might be a vulnerable period for
267 these associations.

268

269 **4.2 Interpretation of main findings**

270 Previous literature hypothesized that exposure to phthalates, which already occurs during the
271 vulnerable fetal period, affects growth and adiposity (Mose et al., 2007; Philips et al., 2017).
272 Previously, we reported, using data from the current cohort study, that prenatal maternal phthalate
273 urine concentrations were associated with fetal growth restriction but were not associated with
274 childhood BMI at 10 years old (Santos et al., 2021; Sol et al., 2020). However, exploring the
275 associations with BMI longitudinally is more important, as adverse BMI development during
276 childhood is a strong predictor of subsequent health outcomes (Barker et al., 2005).

277 Previous studies exploring the associations of maternal phthalate urine concentrations during
278 pregnancy with childhood BMI showed inconsistent results, although the studies including repeated
279 measurements of BMI showed, more often, positive associations (Agay-Shay et al., 2015; Berger et
280 al., 2021; Botton et al., 2016; Bowman et al., 2019; Buckley et al., 2016; Ferguson et al., 2022; Gao et
281 al., 2022; Güil-Oumrait et al., 2022; Harley et al., 2017; Heggeseth et al., 2019; Kupsco et al., 2022;
282 Lee et al., 2022; Lee et al., 2020; Li et al., 2021; Maresca et al., 2016; Shoaff et al., 2017; Sol et al.,
283 2020; Svensson et al., 2021; Vafeiadi et al., 2018; Valvi et al., 2015; Vrijheid et al., 2020; Yang et al.,
284 2017; Yang et al., 2018). In three American studies among 345-536 mother-child pairs, higher second
285 and third trimester maternal urine concentrations of multiple phthalates were associated with higher
286 BMI Z-scores between 4 and 14 years (Harley et al., 2017; Heggeseth et al., 2019; Kupsco et al.,
287 2022). Similarly, in a recent US study among 780 mothers and their children, higher averaged
288 concentrations of first and third trimester maternal phthalate concentrations were associated with
289 higher BMI Z-scores at 3 to 6 years old (Ferguson et al., 2022). Furthermore, in a recent Chinese study
290 among 990 mother-daughter pairs, higher pregnancy-averaged phthalate concentrations were
291 associated with an increased probability of having a high BMI trajectory until 6 years old (Gao et al.,
292 2022). In contrast, a US study among 707 mothers and their children from three cohorts reported that,
293 among girls, higher maternal urine concentrations of mEP and DEHP metabolites were associated with
294 lower BMI Z-scores between 4 to 7 years old (Buckley et al., 2016). Among 657 participants from the
295 Spanish INMA study, the average of first and third trimester maternal urine phthalate concentrations
296 were not associated with BMI Z-scores until 7 years old (Valvi et al., 2015). Furthermore, three
297 previous studies explored weight and height growth instead of BMI. In a French study among 520
298 mother-son pairs, higher second trimester maternal urine mEP concentrations were associated with
299 higher weight growth velocity at two and four years old while in a Swedish study among 1118 mother-
300 child pairs, first trimester maternal phthalate urine concentrations was not associated with weight until
301 5.5 years old (Botton et al., 2016; Svensson et al., 2021). In a German study among 130 mothers and
302 their children, maternal urine phthalate concentrations were again not associated with weight gain in
303 the first two years (Nidens et al., 2021).

304 Finally, some studies explored more specific measurements of adiposity. A US study found
305 that higher maternal phthalate urine concentrations were negatively associated with different measures
306 of adiposity at 5 months old, mostly among boys (Stevens et al., 2023). In a Chinese study among
307 2950 mother-child pairs, however, maternal urine phthalate concentrations during pregnancy were
308 associated with adverse body composition until 6 years old (Gao et al., 2023). In a small Mexican
309 study, there was also an association of higher maternal urine DEHP concentrations with higher
310 adipose mass among boys between 8 to 10 years old (Montes et al., 2022). Finally, a small US study
311 showed no association of maternal phthalate urine concentrations with measures of body composition
312 at 12 years (Etzel et al., 2022).

313 In our study, we found an association of higher maternal HMWP and DEHP urine
314 concentrations with lower age- and sex-adjusted BMI SDS at younger ages. In contrast, higher
315 maternal PA and LMWP urine concentrations were associated with higher age- and sex-adjusted BMI
316 SDS at older ages. Multiple associations have been reported in the literature for maternal DEHP urine
317 concentrations with childhood BMI or weight gain, although these are not consistent over multiple
318 studies (Buckley et al., 2016; Gao et al., 2022; Harley et al., 2017; Heggeseth et al., 2019; Kupsco et
319 al., 2022; Valvi et al., 2015; Yang et al., 2018). This inconsistency between studies might be explained
320 by time-varying effects, i.e., the effect is not apparent across all age periods, which was also observed
321 in our study. Maternal mEP urine concentrations were one of the drivers of the association of LMWP
322 with higher BMI during childhood observed in our study. These results are consistent with multiple
323 studies that have reported associations of mEP with higher BMI or weight growth velocity in either all
324 participants or among boys specifically (Botton et al., 2016; Harley et al., 2017; Heggeseth et al.,
325 2019). Studies that included birth weight in the longitudinal growth assessment have found an
326 association of higher maternal urine phthalate concentrations with lower fetal growth and birth weight
327 combined with changes in postnatal growth trajectories, which could indicate that there is some form
328 of catch-up growth after exposure to phthalates during fetal life (Ferguson et al., 2022; Li et al., 2021;
329 Svensson et al., 2021). Our results are consistent with this hypothesis, since we found that higher
330 maternal urine phthalate concentrations were associated with lower BMI at early postnatal ages but
331 with higher BMI at later ages. In two previous studies that included the same participants as this study,

332 we found that higher maternal phthalate concentrations were associated with fetal growth restriction
333 and we furthermore found that higher maternal first trimester phthalic acid concentrations were
334 associated with higher pericardial fat index at 10 years of age, findings that are also consistent with
335 this hypothesis (Sol et al., 2020). We did not find any sex-specific associations in this study, which is
336 in line with most previous studies.

337 In our study, the largest effect estimates were found for first trimester maternal phthalate urine
338 concentrations, suggesting this might be a vulnerable period for the effects of phthalates. This could be
339 due to the fact that developmental disturbances during the first trimester can have major health
340 implications by causing changes in the development of organ systems with long-lasting health effects.
341 Most previous studies included second or third trimester concentrations or averaged the concentrations
342 over pregnancy and thus lack comparability with ours. Even though the effect estimates presented in
343 this study are small, due to the widespread occurrence of phthalates in our environment and the
344 difficulties of treating obesity and its adverse health consequences once it has developed, our findings
345 are important from a public health perspective.

346

347 **4.3 Potential underlying mechanisms**

348 Many possible mechanisms have been suggested for the associations of maternal phthalate exposure
349 during pregnancy with childhood adiposity. Phthalates are able to interact with the PPARgamma-
350 receptor, which is of high importance in the regulation of adipogenesis (Barak et al., 1999; Feige et al.,
351 2007; Rosen et al., 2002; Taxvig et al., 2012). Since disturbances in fetal growth could lead to an
352 increased risk of obesity later in life and the PPARgamma-receptor is also involved in placental
353 development, effects of phthalates on placental development might also play a role in its association
354 with childhood BMI (Barak et al., 1999; Roseboom et al., 2006). As many phthalates are known to
355 interfere with either the estrogen or androgen receptor, it is also possible that part of the association of
356 prenatal exposure to phthalates occurs via influencing these receptors, although the specific effects
357 could be dependent on the target tissues and could also vary for parent phthalates and their primary or
358 secondary metabolites (Begum and Carpenter, 2022; Engel et al., 2017). Furthermore, phthalates are
359 known to induce oxidative stress and inflammation, which is linked to the development of adiposity

360 (Campioli et al., 2014). Finally, epigenetic changes induced by exposure to phthalates might influence
361 obesity later in life (Manikkam et al., 2013; Martinez-Arguelles et al., 2014).

362

363 **4.4 Methodological considerations**

364 The main advantage of this study was that up to 8 BMI measurements were performed during infancy,
365 childhood and adolescence, giving us the opportunity to assess BMI longitudinally. Our study is also
366 one of the largest population-based cohort studies exploring the associations of phthalates with
367 childhood health to date. Furthermore, we assessed exposure to phthalates at three different times
368 during pregnancy, giving us the opportunity to assess both potential windows of vulnerability and the
369 average exposure during pregnancy. Finally, due to the extensive data collection within the Generation
370 R Study, we were able to adjust for many potential confounders including maternal diet. Of course,
371 there are some limitations to our study. The main limitation of studies that explore the associations of
372 exposure to phthalates, including ours, is that these exposure are highly variable due to their short half-
373 lives (Wang et al., 2019). Nevertheless, it has been reported that for some phthalates such as mEP, the
374 concentration in a spot urine sample could represent exposure up to three months (Hauser et al., 2004).
375 In line with other studies conducted within Generation R on endocrine disruptors and childhood
376 health, we have used a 20% detection rate as the minimum threshold to avoid excluding newer and,
377 therefore, less prevalent chemicals from the analysis. However, as, in this study, the proportion of
378 values below the detection is very low, the influence of the cutoff choice is minimal. Furthermore, we
379 have used single substitution to impute values below the LOD. The use of single substitution could
380 introduce bias if the percentage of values below the LOD is high. Again, as the detection rates in this
381 study are generally high, we expect that this potential bias is of limited relevance in this study. In this
382 study, we used BMI as a proxy for adiposity, while other measurements such as specific fat
383 measurements might be more clearly associated with adiposity and its related health risks. Despite
384 this, the assessment of BMI is both relatively easy to obtain in practice and a reasonable proxy of fat
385 mass (Kakinami et al., 2014). Finally, although we tried to limit bias due to confounding by adjusting
386 for multiple potential confounders in the analysis, residual confounding cannot be excluded.

387

388 **5. CONCLUSIONS**

389 In this study, we found an association of higher maternal first trimester HMWP and DEHP urine
390 concentrations with lower age- and sex-adjusted BMI SDS at younger ages, while higher first
391 trimester maternal phthalic acid and LMWP urine concentrations were associated with higher age- and
392 sex-adjusted BMI SDS at older ages. These results are suggestive of an association of prenatal
393 exposure to phthalates with growth restriction during pregnancy and early in life followed by catch-up
394 growth and obesity later in life.

395

396 6. ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

397 The Generation R Study is conducted by the Erasmus Medical Centre in close collaboration with the
398 School of Law and the Faculty of Social Sciences at the Erasmus University, Rotterdam, the
399 Municipal Health Service, Rotterdam area, and the Stichting Trombosedienst and Artsenlaboratorium
400 Rijnmond (Star-MDC), Rotterdam. We gratefully acknowledge the contribution of children and their
401 parents, general practitioners, hospitals, midwives and pharmacies in Rotterdam.

402 7. SOURCE OF FUNDING

403 The general design of the Generation R Study is made possible by financial support from the Erasmus
404 MC, University Medical Center, Rotterdam, the Netherlands, the Organization for Health Research
405 and Development (ZonMw) and the Ministry of Health, Welfare and Sport. This study was supported
406 by grant R01-ES022972 and R01-ES029779 from the National Institutes of Health (NIH), USA. The
407 content is solely the responsibility of the authors and does not represent the official views of the
408 National Institutes of Health. This work was supported by the European Union's Horizon 2020
409 research and innovation programme under grant agreement 874583 (ATHLETE Project). VWVJ
410 received an additional grant from the European Research Council (ERC Consolidator Grant, ERC-
411 2014-CoG-64916). SS was supported by the European Union's Horizon Europe Research and
412 Innovation Programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie Postdoctoral Fellowship Grant Agreement
413 No. 101109136 (URBANE). Views and opinions expressed are however those of the authors only and
414 do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Research IExecutive Agency
415 (REA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

416 8. AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS

417 **Chalana M. Sol:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Formal analysis, Writing – Original Draft, Writing
418 – Review & Editing.

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422 **Leonardo Trasande:** Resources, Writing – Review & Editing, Supervision, Funding acquisition.

423 **Susana Santos:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Writing – Review & Editing, Supervision.

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557 pregnancy and BMI trajectories. *Pediatr Obes.* 13, 550-557.

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559

560

561 **Table 1.** Maternal urinary concentrations of phthalates during pregnancy.

	First trimester		Second trimester		Third trimester		ICC
	Median (25 th -75 th percentile)	Percentage below LOD (%)	Median (25 th -75 th percentile)	Percentage below LOD (%)	Median (25 th -75 th percentile)	Percentage below LOD (%)	
Phthalic acid (PA) (nmol/L)	343.3 (181.8-730.3)	0.3	931.0 (373.0-1737.9)	0.1	418.6 (204.7-806.6)	0.4	0.20
Low-molecular-weight phthalates (LMWP) (nmol/L)	1087.1 (430.7-2934.9)	-	591.6 (245.2-1512.1)	-	1040.9 (416.2-2637.5)	-	0.36
Monomethylphthalate (mMP) (nmol/L)	30.2 (15.2-54.9)	0.1	19.3 (10.1-35.0)	0.1	22.7 (11.1-44.3)	0.5	0.30
Monoethylphthalate (mEP) (nmol/L)	710.8 (211.8-2509.1)	0.1	380.9 (129.0-1170.8)	0	684.1 (230.5-2172.4)	0	0.40
Mono-isobutylphthalate (mIBP) (nmol/L)	96.4 (43.0-205.4)	0.1	40.8 (21.0-82.6)	0	81.9 (42.2-172.4)	0.3	0.27
Mono-n-butylphthalate (mBP) (nmol/L)	72.5 (30.5-140.2)	0.7	43.9 (25.0-86.9)	0	54.3 (27.9-112.9)	0.1	0.23
High-molecular-weight phthalates (HMWP) (nmol/L)	222.3 (112.7-407.3)	-	134.3 (74.7-250.9)	-	172.7 (95.2-298.3)	-	0.21
Monobenzylphthalate (mBzBP) (nmol/L)	22.5 (9.0-47.4)	8.3	21.0 (8.7-44.3)	1.6	12.3 (4.6-25.4)	3.5	0.25
Mono-hexylphthalate (mHxP) (nmol/L)	0.9 (0.3-2.0)	23.6	NA	>80	NA	>80	NA
Mono-2-heptylphthalate (mHpP) (nmol/L)	2.1 (0.8-5.7)	35.4	NA	>80	NA	>80	NA
Di-2-ethylhexylphthalate (DEHP) (nmol/L)	174.3 (89.3-325.8)	-	98.8 (53.1-188.1)	-	142.9 (77.7-253.5)	-	0.19
Mono-(2-ethyl-5-carboxy-pentyl)phthalate (mECP) (nmol/L)	53.2 (26.7-103.0)	0.1	34.2 (18.7-67.3)	0.1	58.9 (31.0-110.5)	0	0.26
Mono-(2-ethyl-5-hydroxy-hexyl)phthalate (mEHHP) (nmol/L)	41.0 (19.9-79.1)	0.1	19.1 (10.3-37.5)	0.1	35.0 (17.9-678.0)	0.1	0.12
Mono-(2-ethyl-5-oxohexyl)phthalate (mEOHP) (nmol/L)	26.7 (12.1-53.0)	0	25.8 (12.6-56.9)	0	25.0 (13.2-48.2)	0.1	0.10
Mono-[(2-carboxymethyl)-hexyl]phthalate (mCMHP) (nmol/L)	45.9 (24.6-86.6)	0.1	13.4 (7.3-24.0)	0.2	11.3 (6.0-21.1)	1.1	0.14

Di-n-octylphthalate (DNOP) (nmol/L)	-	-	-
Mono(3-carboxypropyl)- phthalate (mCPP) (nmol/L)	5.8 (3.1-11.0)	0	3.5 (2.1-6.8)
		0	7.1 (3.8-12.6)
			0.1
			0.23

562 The ICC was calculated using a single measurement, absolute agreement and two-way mixed effects model. ICC, intraclass correlation coefficients; LOD, limit of detection;
563 NA, not applicable due to >80% of concentrations below limit of detection.

564

565 **Table 2.** Characteristics of participating mothers.

Maternal characteristics	Participants N = 1,379
Age, mean (SD) (years)	30.5 (4.8)
Parity, n (%), nullipara	839 (61.2%)
Ethnicity, n (%), European	846 (61.9%)
Highest education finished, n (%), higher	663 (50.3%)
Smoking during pregnancy, n (%), yes	305 (24.5%)
First trimester smoking, n (%), yes	262 (21.6%)
Second trimester smoking, n (%), yes	135 (11.3%)
Third trimester smoking, n (%), yes	126 (10.7%)
Alcohol consumption during pregnancy, n (%), yes	711 (57.4%)
First trimester alcohol consumption, n (%), yes	603 (49.5%)
Second trimester alcohol consumption, n(%), yes	408 (34.4%)
Third trimester alcohol consumption, n (%), yes	429 (36.5%)
Folic acid use, n (%), yes	887 (80.6%)
Prepregnancy body mass index, median (IQR) (kg/m ²)	22.7 (4.5)
Maternal diet quality score, mean (SD)	7.8 (1.5)
Male child, n (%)	696 (50.5%)

566 Values represent mean (SD), median (IQR), or number of subjects (valid %).

567

568 **Table 3.** Characteristics of participating children.

Number of participants, n	Age at measurement, mean (SD) years)	BMI, median (IQR) (kg/m²)	Overweight/obesity, n (%)
1,131	0.5 (0.0)	17.1 (1.9)	206 (14.9)
1,128	1.0 (0.1)	17.3 (1.8)	197 (17.5)
947	2.1 (0.1)	16.5 (1.8)	189 (20.0)
835	3.1 (0.1)	15.9 (1.6)	132 (15.8)
767	3.8 (0.1)	15.7 (1.8)	126 (16.4)
1,379	5.9 (0.2)	15.8 (1.8)	243 (17.6)
1,124	9.7 (0.3)	16.8 (2.9)	247 (22.0)
980	13.5 (0.3)	18.8 (3.7)	229 (23.4)

569 Values represent mean (SD), median (IQR), or number of subjects (valid %).

570 ° Cutoffs to assess overweight or obesity were based on the WHO cutoffs, including $\geq +1$ SDS for age- and sex-adjusted BMI as having overweight or obesity (de Onis et al.,
571 2007; WHO, 2006).

572

Table 4. Associations of maternal urinary phthalate concentrations during pregnancy with childhood BMI outcomes from 6 months to 13 years old. Final adjusted linear mixed effects model including age-interaction.

	Effect estimate^a (95% CI)	p-value for interaction with child age at BMI measurement	Effect estimate^a (95% CI)	p-value for interaction with child age at BMI measurement	Effect estimate^a (95% CI)	p-value for interaction with child age at BMI measurement
	First trimester		Second trimester		Third trimester	
PA	-0.07 (-0.13; -0.01)*	0.000*	-0.06 (-0.13; 0.01)	0.107	-0.05 (-0.12; 0.01)	0.001*
LMWP	-0.06 (-0.13; 0.00)	0.000*	-0.06 (-0.13; 0.01)	0.016*	-0.06 (-0.13; 0.01)	0.013*
HMWP	-0.10 (-0.16; -0.04)†	0.000*	-0.03 (-0.09; 0.03)	0.242	0.00 (-0.06; 0.06)	0.445
DEHP	-0.10 (-0.16; -0.04)†	0.001*	-0.03 (-0.08; 0.03)	0.495	0.00 (-0.06; 0.06)	0.414
DNOP	-0.08 (-0.13; -0.02)†	0.003*	-0.06 (-0.12; 0.01)	0.224	-0.01 (-0.07; 0.05)	0.975

P-values for the interaction between the exposure and child age at BMI measurement obtained from linear mixed effects models. Main effects reflect the difference in sex- and age-adjusted BMI measures in SDS for an interquartile range increase in each natural log-transformed phthalate metabolite in $\mu\text{mol/g}$ creatinine.

Main effects for the associations of maternal urine phthalate concentrations and child sex- and age-adjusted BMI measurements obtained from linear mixed effects models. Main effects reflect the difference in sex- and age-adjusted BMI measures in SDS for an interquartile range increase in each natural log-transformed phthalate metabolite in $\mu\text{mol/g}$ creatinine.

Models include maternal age, pre-pregnancy BMI, educational level, ethnicity, parity, diet score during pregnancy, diet score during pregnancy, folic acid supplement use, smoking habits and alcohol consumption during pregnancy per trimester and child age at BMI measurement. Models include an interaction term between the exposure concentration and age at BMI measurement, a random intercept for each participant, and a random slope for age at BMI measurement.

^a If there was evidence for a significant interaction of the maternal phthalate urine concentrations with child age at BMI measurement, the effect estimate presented here represents the effect estimate at fictitious age 0 months and the associations were further explored using graphs.

* p-value < 0.05; † significant after correction for multiple testing (p-value threshold of 0.007).

BMI, body mass index; CI, confidence interval; DEHP, di-2-ethylhexylphthalate; DNOP, di-n-octylphthalate; HMWP, high molecular weight phthalates; LMWP, low molecular weight phthalates; PA, phthalic acid.

Figure 1.

